

The Vibrotactile Pitch of Amplitude Modulated Stimuli

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Abstract. The threshold of perception for sinusoidal vibration stimuli exhibits a strong frequency-dependent effect. This phenomenon poses challenges for encoding musical pitch using simple sinusoidal vibrations, as even small frequency variations can lead to significant changes in perceived intensity. Additionally, achieving a comfortable sensation at very low frequencies requires large amplitude movements from haptic devices, which may cause harmonics due to non-linearities in the system. Previous study have demonstrated that using amplitude modulation (AM) with a high-frequency carrier can dramatically flatten the threshold frequency response for the modulated tone. AM has been successfully employed in modern haptic devices designed to assist hearing-impaired individuals in better understanding speech by modulating a carrier tone with the speech signal envelope. We propose that vibrotactile pitch perception could also benefit from AM stimuli. However, it remains uncertain whether a clear perception of pitch can be induced by AM vibration. To investigate this, we are currently conducting an experiment where participants rate the perceived frequency of AM stimuli with varying modulation and carrier frequencies. Preliminary data show promising results, with a strong and significant effect of modulation frequency. These initial findings suggest that musical melodies could be more efficiently coded using AM vibration stimuli.

Keywords: Vibrotactile Pitch, Amplitude Modulation

1 Introduction

Haptic devices have emerged as a potential solution for supplementing musical information via vibration for people with hearing-impairment. However, determining the optimal method for conveying musical pitch through vibrotactile signals remains an open question. Despite the simplicity of sine waves, they come with some challenges. Unlike the auditory system, which relies on numerous frequency-tuned auditory filters, the tactile system predominantly utilizes two types of mechanoreceptors: Meissner corpuscles and Pacinian corpuscles, both sharply tuned around 70 and 250 Hz, respectively. Consequently, the sensory response to vibration is highly sensitive to frequency, resulting in a steep decreasing threshold slope (12 dB per octave) between 20 Hz and 280 Hz [1]. Small changes in frequency significantly impact perceived intensity, and small changes in amplitude affect the vibrotactile pitch [2]. Lamoré et al. [1] demonstrated that using amplitude-modulated (AM) signals can flatten the threshold slope to 6 dB per octave and that low-frequency information can be detected with much lower displacement if carried by a high-frequency vibration. These AM stimuli have also been employed with success in haptic devices designed to assist cochlear implant listeners in better

hearing speech in noisy environments [4], using 50 to 230 Hz carriers modulated with the speech envelope. However, it is still unclear whether AM vibrations can effectively transmit vibrotactile pitch, as well as how the modulation frequency (MF) and carrier frequency (CF) contribute individually and whether they interact with each other. This study aims to address these questions by investigating the individual contributions of the CF and MF on perceived frequency in AM vibrations.

Fig. 1. Frequency ratings for AM vibrations. Coloured circles denote the magnitude of individual mean ratings for each modulating frequency, grouped by carrier frequency. Black lines indicate group means and the standard error of the mean.

2 Methodology

Five participants (average age was 24, $SD=1.67$, 1 male) were asked to rate on an absolute magnitude scale the perceived frequency of stimuli presented on their left hand through a snooker ball coupled to a piezo-electric actuator. The 16 stimuli were fully amplitude modulated vibrations, composed of all the possible combinations of four CF (100, 150, 250 and 350 Hz) and four MF (20, 30, 60 and 90 Hz). Amplitude was set to a comfortable perceived-intensity-matched level on a pre-experiment procedure with three participants. White noise was delivered through headphones to mask the sound of any vibration stimuli. After completing 20 practice trials, participants were then presented with eight blocks, each containing the 16 stimuli in a random order, for a total of 128 trials. We decided to use the term ‘frequency’ to probe vibrotactile pitch, given the challenge of assigning ‘pitch’ to a complex and purely tactile sensation.

3 Results and Discussion

Individual ratings were normalized by dividing them by the mean rating across participants for each stimulus. Figure 1 presents the ratings for each condition. On average, ratings increase monotonically with MF, suggesting that vibrotactile pitch can be effectively conveyed through this parameter, particularly for CF below 200 Hz. However, for higher CF, the ratings of some participants did not increase monotonically with increasing MF, specifically, one out of five at 250 Hz and three out of five at 350 Hz. A within-subjects, repeated measures, two-way ANOVA was conducted to investigate the effects of MF and CF on perceived frequency ratings. The analysis revealed a strong significant effect of MF ($F(3,12) = 10.142$, $p = .0013$), explaining 43.414% of the variance. A smaller yet significant effect of CF ($F(3,12) = 5.207$, $p = .016$), accounting for 16.347% of the variance. No interaction between CF and MF was found.

The diminished effect of MF for three participants at the highest CF might be explained by the coding mechanisms of pitch. Some research supports a 'ratio code' model, in which pitch increases are driven by the relative activation of Meissner and Pacinian corpuscles [3]. With a 350 Hz carrier, as all signal energy exceeds the sensitivity range of the Pacinian channel and falls outside the Meissner channel's range, we would not expect a change in the activation ratio with MF, and therefore no increase in pitch.

To ensure that all stimuli were perceived with equal intensity during the experiment, we conducted a preliminary procedure involving three participants. They were asked to adjust the amplitude of each stimulus until the perceived intensity was matched. The maximum average difference between the amplitudes of any two stimuli was 11.5 dB. This dynamic range is approximately 3 to 4 times smaller than the expected difference in amplitude for sinusoidal vibrations ranging from 20 to 90 Hz [1], confirming that the perceived intensity of AM stimuli is less affected by the frequency.

In conclusion, our preliminary data suggests that AM stimuli could be efficient to convey musical pitch and that modulating frequency has a greater impact on perceived frequency ratings than carrier frequency.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest relevant to the content of this paper.

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